

Plant-based

Fermentation

Cultivated

Denmark's alternative protein research ecosystem

Alternative proteins – plant-based, fermentation-derived or cultivated – offer a promising solution to meet the projected growth in the global demand for meat, seafood, eggs, and dairy, while building a more sustainable food system.

388 publications

#5 in publication volume in Europe
+461% from 2020 to 2025

433 patents

#6 in published patent volume in Europe

Total public funding

Million € · 2020-2025

Funding per capita

€ per person · 2020-2025

If the EU makes alternative proteins a strategic priority, the sector could contribute significantly to the bloc's economy by 2040.

€111B

annual economic contribution

+400,000

jobs supported